

ENHANCING THERMOSTABILITY OF ALPHA-AMYLASE FROM *BACILLUS LICHENIFORMIS* 104.K FOR INDUSTRIAL APPLICATIONS

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Introduction:

Alpha-amylase is an important enzyme used in various industries, including food, textiles, and detergents, due to its ability to break down starch into sugars [1-4]. The industrial demand for thermostable enzymes is growing, as high-temperature processes can increase reaction efficiency and reduce contamination risks. This study focuses on enhancement of the α -amylase thermostability synthesized by *Bacillus licheniformis* 104.K strain, which is known as producer of thermotolerant enzyme [5-7].

Materials and Methods:

The *Bacillus licheniformis* 104.K strain was screened for α -amylase activity, and the amyL gene encoding the enzyme was cloned and expressed in *Bacillus subtilis* 168. The recombinant enzyme's thermostability and catalytic efficiency were tested at various temperatures. Additionally, computational tools like AlphaFold2 and ProteinMPNN were used to predict and enhance the enzyme's structure and stability [8, 9].

Results:

The crude α -amylase from *B. licheniformis* 104.K exhibited maximum activity at 90°C, retaining a significant portion of its activity after 30 minutes at 70°C. Cloning and expression of the amyL gene in *B. subtilis* 168 expression host, resulted in a highly active recombinant enzyme, with a 170-fold increase in amylase activity (63 U/mL) compared to the native form. Structural prediction using AlphaFold2 showed a high pLDDT score of 94.7 and pTM score of 0.949, confirming the stability of the enzyme. Computational design further enhanced thermostability by optimizing hydrophobic core residues, with positive $\Delta\Delta G$ values indicating greater thermal resistance.

Discussion and conclusion:

The study confirms the industrial potential of *B. licheniformis* 104.K α -amylase due to its high thermostability and activity at elevated temperatures [10]. The enzyme's stability makes it an ideal candidate for applications in harsh industrial conditions [11]. Ongoing research aims to synthesize the engineered amyL gene and further evaluate the thermostability of designed variants, potentially leading to even more robust enzymes for industrial processes.

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